

ENGLISH AND UZBEK DICTIONARIES AND THEIR ORTHOGRAPHY

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Annotation: *One of the fastest growing areas of lexicography today is the field of educational lexicography. The distinguishing feature of educational dictionaries from other dictionaries is that they are directly related to education and have already become an integral part of the field of education. The main task of textbooks is to express language skills to students in a simpler, clearer and, of course, engaging way. The purpose of the article is to define the essence of the concept of lexicography, its place among other linguistic disciplines, to show its great potential in mastering a foreign language as a means of intercultural communication.*

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The field of lexicography is one of the main tools for showing the level of development of any country. Because any development and progress in the economic, political, social, national and cultural spheres of the country is reflected in the dictionaries belonging to the representatives of this nation. Educational lexicography is one of the fastest growing areas of lexicography today. V.V Morkovkin divided general dictionaries into two types. These are anthropocentric and linguocentric dictionaries. The main emphasis in anthropocentric dictionaries is to illuminate the language in the human mind, to help it use it correctly and effectively. In linguocentric dictionaries, language is the main focus and its main function is to explain the facts in that language;

1. Currently, dictionaries are included in the category of anthropocentric dictionaries. Educational dictionaries are designed for the field of education, and these types of dictionaries help students not only to increase their vocabulary, oral or written literacy, but also to develop their creative thinking skills and broaden their worldview. also serves. For example, the Uzbek Vocabulary Dictionary is a great help for students in separating words into stems and suffixes. It is important for students to know exactly what the root of the word is when they use it, and to learn how to add suffixes correctly and use them correctly in language. The dictionary also includes lexemes that are originally mastered, but have Uzbek suffixes, and can be distinguished into stems and suffixes.

2. Currently, there is a genre of complex educational dictionaries in the world educational dictionary. Dictionaries of this type are characterized by the fact that words reflect almost all aspects of one word, not just one.

3. The advantage of this type of dictionary is that the student can study several linguistic features of a single lexeme at the same time using a single dictionary. We've covered some of the features of dictionaries above. In addition, of course, there are some differences between educational dictionaries and other basic dictionaries. In general, dictionaries are divided into large, medium and small dictionaries. Educational dictionaries are mainly small and in some cases medium in size. Because we know that dictionaries are important for students in the educational process (especially in the school field) and can be a tool for them to later access academic dictionaries. If the dictionaries are too large and complex in size, it may not be able to attract students to the field of lexicography. It is important that textbooks are relevant to the field of education and that they are adapted to the textbooks.

In modern linguistics, the term lexicography has several meanings. Firstly, it is a branch of linguistics that studies the theoretical problems of compiling dictionaries of various types. Secondly, this is the direct practice of compiling dictionaries, and thirdly, the totality of dictionaries of various types that a particular country has.

The experience of English lexicography, one of the richest in the world, deserves the closest attention. Analyzing the general trends in the development of vocabulary in England in the period from the 15th to the 20th centuries. the following main groups of functions performed by lexicography can be distinguished:

1. Educational and didactic functions associated with the study:

- a) cultural languages of the Middle Ages, primarily Latin;
- b) modern foreign languages (German, French and others);
- c) English.

2. Functions related to the description and normalization of the English language, carried out by explanatory, orthoepic, ideographic dictionaries, speech correctness dictionaries and some others.

3. Ideological functions that testify to the awareness of the cultural and political role of dictionaries in the accumulation, storage and transmission of cultural and historical heritage from generation to generation.

The wide range of tasks solved by English lexicography testifies to its enormous influence on the formation of the national language, on the entire course of the socio-economic, political, and cultural and historical development of society. In fact, lexicography is a key section of linguistics, accumulating the achievements of lexicology, grammar, stylistics, pragmatics, history of language and many other sciences. Unlike lexicology, which describes the vocabulary of a language as a kind of macrosystem, lexicography, as a collection of dictionaries of different types, aims to give the fullest possible and comprehensive description of each individual lexical unit

of the language, its etymological, grammatical, orthoepic, semantic and other characteristics. Lexicography eliminates the traditional separation of lexicology from grammar; Since the dictionary is also a grammatical reference, lexicographers describe complex and diverse types of interactions of lexical and grammatical meanings in dictionaries. It should be noted that the data of lexicology, grammar, stylistics, pragmatics and other sciences are used by lexicographers not mechanically, but creatively. Vocabulary work requires a special linguistic flair from lexicographers, which is largely akin to writing talent. As a result, dictionaries that accumulate and summarize the achievements of linguistic

Sciences, are transformed from practical reference books into the most important tool for a complete theoretical description of the national language. A distinctive feature of modern lexicography is the synthesis of philology and culture, the expansion of theoretical and research work carried out by the leading publishing houses of Great Britain, America and Russia, the widespread use of computer technology and, as a result, the emergence of a huge number of dictionaries of various types. Thus, at least a hundred new dictionaries appear annually on the book market in English-speaking countries. The status of modern lexicography as an independent science is evidenced by the existence of such sections as general lexicography, bilingual, synonymous, ideographic, scientific and technical, educational (according to foreign terminology, pedagogical), as well as relatively new electronic lexicography or cyberlexicography [1].

Not being able to give a complete description of the educational dictionaries available on the book market, we will consider as an example the Macmillan English Dictionary for Advanced Learners [3], which reflects all the achievements of modern English educational lexicography. First, on the basis of a computer database of 20 million word usages, a careful selection of a vocabulary of 100,000 lexical units and 30,000 idiomatic expressions was made. Secondly, the dictionary clearly defines the quantitative and qualitative parameters of the active core of the vocabulary, which has about 7,500 lexical units. The core includes frequency vocabulary to express the most important concepts, realities, etc. In the corpus of the dictionary, such words are typed in red, the frequency of their use in speech is indicated by the corresponding number of asterisks (from 1 to 3, depending on the rating).

Thirdly, the lexicographic portrait of any of the 100,000 words is described using a carefully selected lexical minimum, the so-called "defining vocabulary" of 2,500 words. This list of words for interpretation of meanings is placed at the end of the dictionary. The foregoing clearly indicates the undeniable merits of the educational dictionary in comparison, for example, with a general-purpose explanatory dictionary. First, in

The dictionary uses an original way of presenting vocabulary for active and passive learning - the red color of the title word tells the student that this word should

be learned first. A dictionary entry with a red heading word is distinguished by a large volume - it contains the necessary additional information: phonetic, grammatical, stylistic, as well as examples illustrating morpho-syntactic and lexical-phraseological compatibility, which helps the student to adequately use this word in independent statements. Secondly, the clarity and clarity of the definitions of the words placed in the dictionary is achieved through the use of a minimum selected on a scientific basis, which is assumed to have been learned by the student at the previous stage. As an illustration, here is one of the short dictionary entries, for example: Privilege [privslidg] noun

1 [C] A special benefit that is available only to a particular person or group:

Cheep air travel is one of the privileges of working for the airline. The country should extend trade privileges to its poorer neighbors.

1. a. Something nice that you feel lucky to have: it's been a privilege to be involved in such an interesting project.

2. b. Something that only a particular type of person is allowed to do: He was exercising over of an old man to be as rude as he liked.

3. [U] Way of life that involved having many advantages and opportunities, without working hard for them: a life of privilege.

4. [U] A situation in which lawyers, doctors, and other professional people are legally allowed to keep their discussions with people secret: doctor-patient privilege.

Pay / be charged for the privilege to have to pay for something, usually when this does seem fair: they expect us to live in a smaller house and pay more money for the privilege. Words frequently used with privilege: verbs: abuse, confer, enjoy, exercise grant, have, invoke, limit, waive [3, p.1121].

Our brief review of modern active-type dictionaries cannot be considered complete without mentioning a large group of encyclopedic dictionaries in the English language. The recognition by linguists of the special function of a foreign language as a means of intercultural communication requires the widespread use of linguistic, cultural, encyclopedic and other dictionaries in the university educational process [9]. These dictionaries contain extensive extralinguistic information, acquaint students with the history, culture, traditions and other national features of the country, and thus contribute to the creation of a common base with native speakers for free communication with foreigners.

Thus, the system of dictionaries proposed by us, which reflects the latest scientific achievements not only in linguistics, but also in many other sciences, including the natural sciences, the proven methodology for working with them will allow introducing elements of innovative technologies into the university educational process, organizing independent work of students and effectively managing it, which will contribute to improving the quality of training in foreign languages. It should be noted that the experience of using these dictionaries can be useful for students of the

Faculty of Foreign Languages in their work with English-German and German-English dictionaries and, of course, will make it easier for them to master the German language in a shorter time. The foregoing indicates the need to introduce a mandatory theoretical course in lexicography at the initial stage of higher education, as is practiced in a number of universities in the country. This course will introduce students to the history of foreign lexicography, the main problems of the theory and practice of vocabulary, help them better navigate the huge mass of modern lexicographic products, choose the right type of dictionary and quickly get the information you need. In our opinion, future teachers and translators are obliged to acquire the necessary skills of vocabulary work and improve them within the walls of the university, since their profession involves systematic work with dictionaries of various types in their further independent activity.

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